

Assessments of the status of Water Bodies in Wetlands by Citizen Scientists

Guideline and Protocols

Version 1.1

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Chapter 1: Background

Monitoring Ecosystem Services (ES) provided by wetlands is crucial for assessing the state of the wetlands, their changes over time, and the impacts of conservation and restoration measures. The engagement of non-experts as Citizen Scientists can support this ES monitoring by delivering large amounts of data otherwise not (easily) available. Additionally, Citizen Science helps raise awareness among local people about the significance of wetlands for human well-being, thereby enhancing citizens' stewardship.

In the Horizon Europe Project **RESTORE4LIFE**, 101112736 (<https://restore4life.eu/>), we have created a **toolbox for monitoring ES of wetlands** (Deliverable D3.5), covering both geospatial and on-the-ground methods (publicly available from Dec 2025 on our webpage and Zenodo). One focus was on developing Citizen Science protocols for on-the-ground measurements that provide reliable and valuable data for wetland assessments. Various Citizen Scientists helped us test the developed protocols regarding their intelligibility, user-friendliness, and applicability before release. To assess the quality and explanatory power of the data collected by Citizen Scientists, we compared them with data collected by scientists using more advanced methods. The results of these quality checks can be found in our toolbox D3.5.

The following topics were covered and published separately: (1) water body quality, (2) organic carbon storage in tree biomass and wetland soils, (3) plant diversity, and (4) recreational and educational services. Each published document consists of several parts: Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for assessing data in the field; Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for indoor analyses (if applicable); Citizen Scientists' protocol(s) for calculations (if applicable); and a guideline for scientists on further data processing.

The current document addresses the **status of water bodies**, including **water quality**, in wetlands.

Chapter 2: Water bodies in wetlands

Water bodies in wetlands are crucial for the **ecological health, biodiversity, and functionality** of these unique ecosystems: Water bodies in wetlands are habitats for a wide variety of flora and fauna and used as breeding and nursery grounds by fish, amphibians, and birds. They trap sediments and pollutants, adsorb nutrients, and allow clean water to seep slowly into groundwater or flow into rivers. Wetlands act like sponges, absorbing excess rainfall and runoff, reducing the risk and severity of floods. The stored water is released gradually, maintaining base flows in rivers and streams during dry periods.

Water bodies in wetlands come in **various forms**, depending on the geography, hydrology, and ecological characteristics of the area. Here are the main types of water bodies found in wetlands:

- ◇ 1. **Ponds:** Shallow, still water bodies often found in marshes and swamps. Can be permanent or seasonal (i.e. dry out).
- ◇ 2. **Lakes:** Larger than ponds and may extend beyond wetland boundaries. Wetlands often form around lake margins, where water levels fluctuate.
- ◇ 3. **Rivers and Streams:** Flowing water bodies that pass through or border wetlands.
- ◇ 4. **Oxbow Lakes and Cut-off Channels** (former parts of the river): Curved, isolated water bodies formed when a river changes course; common in floodplains; often become stagnant or seasonal wetlands over time.
- ◇ 5. **Marsh Pools:** Small, shallow pools found within freshwater or saltwater marshes. Usually seasonal, filling during wet periods.
- ◇ 6. **Swamps (Forested Wetlands):** Contain standing or slow-moving water and are dominated by trees or shrubs. Water may be present year-round or seasonally. Often have a mix of open water channels and vegetated areas.
- ◇ 7. **Bogs and Fens (Peatlands):** Acidic (bogs) or alkaline (fens) wetlands that often have small water pools or open areas. Water comes from rainfall (bogs) or groundwater (fens).
- ◇ 8. **Tidal Channels and Coastal Lagoons:** Found in coastal and estuarine wetlands (e.g., mangroves and salt marshes). Include tidal creeks, inlets, and brackish lagoons. Influenced by tidal action, mixing freshwater and seawater.
- ◇ 9. **Vernal Pools (Seasonal Wetlands):** Small, temporary water bodies that form in spring from rain or snowmelt. Dry up in summer, but are vital for certain plant and animal life.
- ◇ 10. **Man-made Wetland Water Bodies:** Includes reservoirs, canals, rice paddies, fish ponds, or constructed wetlands. Often created for water management, agriculture, or conservation.

Chapter 3: Assessing the Hydro-morphology of Water bodies

3.1. OUTDOOR PROTOCOL

MATERIALS:

- ❖ Smartphone
- ❖ Notepad
- ❖ Virtual / Analog Map
- ❖ GPS-enabled device (Internet access for location tracking)
- ❖ Evaluation Form

TASKS:

1. Select a **water body larger than 4 m in width and 4 m in length**. You can measure the distance by taking large steps.
2. Note the GPS data of the water body
3. Take pictures from different points of the water body to provide a good overview (if possible)
4. Fill in the form.

We appreciate your support!

The following questionnaire provides information on the type, structure, size, and hydrology of a water body. This helps us identify its potential as a habitat for different plant and animal species and its role in water purification and retention.

Human activities inform us about current pressures that may threaten the health of the water body.

EVALUATION FORM			
Name / Pseudonym:			
Date:		Time:	
Name of location:		GPS data of water body:	
Type of nature reserve (lake, wetland, forest, etc.)			

1) Is the water body:

- natural men-made I do not know

2) How does the water body smell?

- like flowers
 like a fish
 like wet earth
 like a dead body
 I smell nothing

3) Do you see signs of human activities?

- no
 yes, I see:

- | | |
|---|---|
| <input type="checkbox"/> Waste on the shore | <input type="checkbox"/> Information signs |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Waste buckets | <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering structures (dam, levee, ...) |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Boats | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Bridge | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Walking path | <input type="checkbox"/> |

4) Water body type: Which description fits best?

Type	Description	Scheme	
River, stream	Elongated; water is flowing through a curved channel; usually no swimming water plants due to current;		
Lake	Large, often round or oval water body; water is not flowing (but wind may cause some movement on the surface); swimming water plants		
Pond	Smaller than a lake, water is not flowing; swimming water plants often distributed over the entire water surface		
Oxbow lake (former meander of the river)	looks like a river channel, but the water is not flowing;		
Peatlands/Fens/Bogs	Thick stands of mosses and grasses with small pools and open water areas in between		
Swamp	Standing or slow-moving water with trees and shrubs growing in it		
Other			

5) Water velocity: If you see water flowing, select a 10 m long section along the shore (approximately 10 large steps). Mark the section with sticks. Throw a stick into the water at the upstream part and measure the time it takes for the stick to reach the end of the section.

- slow flow (>1min) medium flow fast flow (<15 sec)

6) Which types of water plants do you see? (more options possible)

- no plants growing in the water
- only dead water plants visible
- Water plants swimming on the surface (e.g. water lilies, water lenses)
- Water plants totally submerged in the water
- Water plants submerged in the water but flowers/leaves reach out of the water
- Water plants only with their roots and lower stem inside the water (e.g. reed, cattail)

7) Do you see dead wood in the water?

- yes, many large trunks
- yes, 1-2 large trunks
- only small twigs
- no

8) How would you describe the water body?

	1	2	3	4	5	
Heterogeneous natural shoreline						Shoreline homogenous and artificial
Clean water						Waste flowing in the water
Water transparent						Water murky, brown or green
Heavily shaded						Fully exposed to sunlight

9) How would you describe the water level?

Description	Scheme	
<p>High water level: the water level is above the line of terrestrial plants; trees, shrubs, and grasses on the banks are standing in the water</p>		
<p>Mean water level: the water level is more or less at the line of terrestrial plants</p>		
<p>Low water level: the water level is clearly below the line of terrestrial plants; parts of the usually submerged shoreline are above the water level, revealing muddy banks covered by algae</p>		
<p>Extremely low water level: only small parts of the water body are covered by shallow water</p>		

Chapter 4: Assessing the Water Quality

4.1. OUTDOOR PROTOCOL

MATERIALS:

- ❖ Clean ca. 500 mL plastic bottle with a small rope tied to the neck of the bottle and a weight (e.g., a padlock) so that the bottle sinks under the water
- ❖ Clean turbidity tube
- ❖ Clean and transparent water color tube and color scheme
- ❖ Advanced: Nutrient and dissolved oxygen test kits; funnel, coffee filter, plastic beaker

OUTDOOR TASKS:

1. **Picture:** Select a place where you can easily sample the water without stepping into it. Take a picture of the location and the water body with your smartphone.
2. **Water body location and type:** Determine your location with your smartphone's GPS. Fill in the data in the water quality form and add information about the water body and its surroundings. Use one form per site.
3. **Water sampling:** Hold the rope's end and throw the open plastic bottle into the water (about 1-2m from the banks). Let the bottle fill with water and pull it back to the shore without disturbing the bottom. Repeat this procedure twice before using the sample for the following steps.
4. **Water-color:** Fill the sample water into the transparent test tube and hold it against the color scheme. Let the sample stand for a few minutes to allow the particles to settle. Note down the color and the brightness in the form. Take a picture of the sample tube against the color scheme.
Note: This should be best done in full sunlight. If the sky is cloudy, note it in your form.

5. Visibility depth with the turbidity tube:

A Mini-Secchi tube (or turbidity tube) is a transparent tube of approx. 0.5 to 1 m with a black-white pattern at the bottom. Ideally, the tube has an opening at the bottom to release water.

Procedure:

Stand with your back to the sun. Fill the tube until it is full of water. **CAREFUL: Do not disturb the bottom of the water body while sampling.**

Now, look through the tube and **slowly release water** until you see the black-white pattern appear at the bottom.

Note the **height of the water** in the tube in cm.

If the black-white pattern is visible when the tube is full, record the length of the entire tube.

INDOOR TASKS – ADVANCED WATER CHEMISTRY:

- Nutrients:** If the water is very turbid (Secchi value >75), filter the sample for nutrient analysis through the coffee filter into the clean beaker. Use the funnel as a filter holder. Follow the test kit's instructions for nitrate and phosphate analyses. Note the values in the form.
- Dissolved Oxygen:** Follow the test kit's instructions for determining dissolved oxygen concentrations and note the values in the form.

Thank you!

Color scheme:

	Light	Medium	Dark
No colour			
Green (algae)			
Brown (organic matter)			
Grey (mineral matter)			

Water quality form			
Name / ID:			
Date:		Time:	
Name of water body/area:		GPS data:	
Waterbody type ¹ :		Flow ² :	
Land use ³ :		Bank vegetation ⁴ :	
Dead wood in the water		Foam, floating algae, litter and oily sheen	
Evidence of water uses (e.g. fishing, swimming)		Pollution sources in the surroundings	
Water colour ⁵		Turbidity tube value	
Dissolved oxygen (mg/L)			
Nitrate (mg/L)		Phosphate (mg/L)	
Comments:			

¹ Lake, pond, isolated backwater, river, stream, ditch, other (describe)

² no flow; slow, medium, fast

³ Forest, meadows, agriculture, urban, other (describe)

⁴ Reed, herbs and grasses, trees, none

⁵ no colour, greenish, brownish, greyish; light, medium, dark

4.2. BACKGROUND INFORMATION

Water bodies in floodplain forests tend to be highly productive. This means they process large amounts of organic input from their surroundings, such as fallen leaves and other plant material. **As a result, the water may appear more brownish or greenish compared to, for example, clear mountain streams.**

However, increased coloration is not necessarily a sign of poor water quality. These waters can **still be in good ecological condition**, both for the specific habitat they represent and for the surrounding ecosystems, despite their stronger coloration. Respectively, elevated nutrient-levels may occur as a natural consequence of bio-input into alluvial water bodies.

Nonetheless, measuring water-quality (nutrient abundance, oxygen dissolution, etc.) can indicate input from agriculture, forestry or other forms of land use. Regular monitoring can support early detection of environmental pressures and contribute to the long-term conservation of these dynamic ecosystems.

4.3. FOR SCIENTISTS

There is a large number of different test kits. Our recommendations:

The concentration range, which can be measured with the **kit**, should suit the actual concentration range of your water bodies. Use complete sets, including all required parameters, only for small groups of well-trained CS who take repeated measurements. Each CS gets their own set. For larger groups, which sample only once or twice, combine individual packs into a set. Always test the kits before distributing them to the citizens.

You can easily construct a **turbidity tube** by yourself (see e.g. the reference). There are also numerous YouTube videos in the internet. The best tubes have an opening at the bottom to release water (as described in the protocol). This is easier than filling water gradually into the tube and watching the disappearance of the disk. An alternative with a closed tube would be to have a separate mini-secchi disk attached to a thin rope which you lower into the tube. Below, you can find the NTU conversion table.

Conversion of cm into NTU values

(<https://extension.usu.edu/waterquality/utahwaterwatch/turbidity-tube-converstion-chart> 16.10.2025)

Distance from Bottom of Tube (cm)	NTUs
<6.25	>240
6.27 to 7	240
7 to 8	185
8 to 9.5	150
9.5 to 10.5	120
10.5 to 12	100
12 to 13.75	90
13.75 to 16.25	65
16.25 to 18.75	50
18.75 to 21.25	40
21.25 to 23.75	35
23.75 to 26.25	30
26.25 to 28.75	27
28.75 to 31.25	24

31.25 to 33.75	21
33.75 to 36.25	19
36.25 to 38.75	17
38.75 to 41.25	15
41.25 to 43.75	14
43.75 to 46.25	13
46.25 to 48.75	12
48.75 to 51.25	11
51.25 to 53.75	10
53.75 to 57.5	9
57.5 to 60	8
Over the top	6

REFERENCES

<https://manoa.hawaii.edu/exploringourfluidearth/sites/default/files/pd-forum-attachments/Turbidity%20Tube.pdf>